

THEORETICAL PRINCIPLES OF IMPROVING STUDENTS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCES BASED ON INTEGRATIVE EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES

Shodiev M. B.

Researcher, Tashkent state pedagogical university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13902316>

Abstract. *Specific aspects, situation, purpose, tasks of teaching students of higher educational institutions for communicative competence and the main requirements for integrative education were studied. State requirements that students should acquire and difficulties in acquiring it were analyzed.*

Keywords: *interactive, communicative, competence, education, technology, intellectual, interactive method.*

In the general requirements of the state educational standard of higher education for the content of academic subjects, blocks, it is necessary to ensure that the process of education and training is oriented towards the formation of an independent thinking, capable of making decisions, comprehensively developed, well-rounded person. given importance. Of course, these requirements include raising the educational process in higher educational institutions to a higher level, implementing teaching based on new methods, improving students' ability to think independently, communicative competence, and raising the level of knowledge through professional skills. requires quality performance. At the same time, an innovative approach to the formation of pedagogical competence and creativity of students and the use of modern information technologies are becoming a priority. The purpose of our research is to determine the content, forms and methods of the innovative approach to increase the effectiveness of students' communicative competence formation and to widely implement them in practice through experimental work.

The status of educational technology in society is increasing day by day, and its functions are expanding. Innovative technologies are considered as a means of intercultural communication, as well as one of the leading components of the professional competence of every specialist, in terms of accelerating the globalization and integration processes taking place worldwide.

In order to improve the quality of education in the world, the need to apply international standards, to modernize the teaching content, to ensure the harmony of education and innovation, and to use modern pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process is growing. Nowadays, knowledge of a foreign language is not only a sign of cultural development of a person, but also a factor of success in his professional activity and in various other fields.

In our republic, great attention is paid to teaching on the basis of innovative technologies, and the expansion of cooperation relations of our republic with foreign countries in various fields in all educational institutions requires perfect mastery of the language from every specialist and direct communication with foreign colleagues. requires that they can communicate.

In the current qualitative process of development, educational programs, textbooks and methodical manuals are being created that meaningfully ensure the continuity and coherence between the stages of education. Great attention is being paid to increasing the efficiency of

education by using innovative technologies in teaching subjects. As a result of these efforts, the most modern pedagogical technologies and ICT technologies were introduced into the educational process, the teaching method was fundamentally changed, the subject of education (teacher and students) was activated, independent, innovative technologies that encourage creative thinking were introduced into the educational process.

It should be noted that today the competence approach is widely applied to the teaching process of all subjects. Now it has become clear that it is not enough to give students knowledge, skills and qualifications in science, but it is necessary to develop the skills of practical application of the acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications in various situations. A unique aspect of education at a higher educational institution is the training of competitive pedagogues with a high level of communicative competence. Knowing and using innovative technologies is one of the important conditions for the existence of demand for modern students. Education through the competence approach is education aimed at improving the ability to apply acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in their personal, professional and social activities, and students have independent thinking and an active citizenship position. learning, initiative, the ability to use innovative technologies in education in their work, conscious choice of profession, healthy competition and general cultural skills.

Today, every student's perfect mastery of the learning process with competency-based approaches lays the groundwork for him to achieve great success both in his work and in his personal life. Learning a language other than the mother tongue, studying the culture, art, science, technical achievements, political, economic, spiritual and educational aspects of the people helps to increase the scope of human thinking and worldview.

Basically, the research work of T.P.Popova tried to reveal the differences between the terms "competence" and "competency". In addition, the purpose of communicative competence, its types, structure and levels are divided into groups and scientifically substantiated.

A.T.Nurmanov believes that theoretical, personological, technological, individual, differentiated, emotional, rational, reproductive, productive, systematic, person-oriented and competence approaches are important for effective communication of students.

The application of competence as a scientific category to education is an important factor, and N.A.Muslimov said that the approach from the point of view of competence is one of the bases for improving professional education. Today, not only professional skills consisting of the skills to perform one or another technological process are required, but competence consisting of a combination of professional and personal qualities such as professional skills, social ethics, ability to work in a team, and initiative.

Competent approach harmoniously combines with many approaches of modern education and gives a person the opportunity to show his personal potential in the form of self-expression and social interaction.

J.Raven, one of the founders of the competence approach, stated: "when we compare more and less competent farmers, teachers, drivers, managers and military officers, in each case the political behavior demonstrated by the masters of their work is the most turned out to be important. On the contrary, the inability and unwillingness of people to take action against social, organizational and political constraints outside the scope of their immediate duties appears to be the main source of incompetent professional behavior in modern society, even though it is within this framework that they determine what they can do.

REFERENCES

1. Oliy ta'lim tizimini 2030 yilgacha takomillashtirish konsepsiyasi to'g'risida. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining PF-5847-son Farmoni. 2019 yil 8 oktyabr.
2. Pedagogik ta'lim sohasini yanada takomillashtirish to'g'risidagi chora-tadbirlar to'g'risida. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining PQ-4623-son Qarori. 2020 yil 27 fevral.
3. Попова Т.П. Формирование иноязычной коммуникативной компетенции у студентов заочного отделения языкового вуза. Монография. – Н.Новгород, 2013. – 186 с.
4. Nurmanov A.T. Talabalarning samarali muloqot texnologiyasi va texnikasiga tayyorlashning pedagogik imkoniyatlari (auditoriyadan tashqari mashg'ulotlar misolida): Avtoref...diss. ...ped. fan. dokt. – T., 2017. – 29 b.
5. Muslimov N.A. Kasb ta'limi o'qituvchisini kasbiy shakllantirishning nazariy-metodik asoslari: Dis. ... ped. fan. dok. – T., 2007. – 349 b.
6. Pedagogik ta'lim innovatsion klasteri: ehtiyoj, zarurat, natija. Elektron resurs: <https://xs.uz/uzkr/post/pedagogik-talim-innovatsion-klasteri-ehtiyozh-zarurat-natizha>. Murojaat sanasi: 08.06.2021.